

OPEN**Experiences of Student Journalists During the Covid-19 Pandemic**Rodel C. Pacit¹ and Dr John Erwin P. Pedroso¹

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the human beings in the community. Student journalists are the ones who endured many challenges in their publication work. They acquired experiences that develop their capacity to cope from difficult situations. Hence, this study ascertained the experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. The qualitative-phenomenological approach of research design was employed using a researcher-made written interview form administered through messenger and email among five (5) purposively selected editors-in-chief from different universities and state colleges. The environmental, technological, and psychological experiences of the student journalists were revealed. There were six (6) meaningful categories taken from data transcripts. Student journalists were able to (1) manifest positive outlook in life and (2) render democratic community empowerment services as their environment-related experiences. Besides, their media technology-related experiences included (3) adjust to unprecedented working transition and (4) encounter misinformation and disinformation. Finally, they acquired psychology-related experiences such as (5) confront social communication disparity and (6) endure from self-efficacy enervation. Since student journalists facing many challenges, they still show their willingness to serve the school and the community during hard times. Thus, student journalists' roles and responsibilities are to deliver factual information and help the people in the society.

Keywords: Experiences, student journalists, challenges, school publication, COVID-19 pandemic

Introduction

Student journalists embody various efforts to cover relevant development and issues amid the current global crisis. They use their vocal and physical power to deliver factual information and inspiring stories to the people. As agents of truth and consciousness, student journalists have crucial functions in spreading awareness in global

and online communities (Wu, 2020). However, the COVID-19 pandemic brings struggles to student journalists wherein they encountered certain difficulties in obtaining responses from interviewees, as well as working with the colleagues for school paper publication (Joung, 2020). The student journalists avoid

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physical conducting of interviews because they may be potentially exposing themselves to the virus. As a wise alternative, they come up with unique yet creative ways to interact with people in getting stories and salient pieces of information. As a result, student journalists do their job, even though they are confronted by the COVID-19 challenges (Mook, 2020).

In the past two years, there is 44% of teachers who reported a sudden rise in journalism class enrollment and more than 30% increase in students' interest who majored journalism in universities and colleges. Because of this, journalism students are encouraged by the academic curriculum to focus more on state and local news that can lead to a more productive dialogue inside the class. Thus, students acquire more opportunity to cover and influence community events (Jones, 2019). Several studies about student journalism have strictly concentrated on emphasizing the roles and significance of student journalism in the school curriculum and student skills development. Campus student journalism promotes life-long learning that enhanced both academics and life skills essential to the lives of the students. Nevertheless, campus journalists' expressions of ideas are censored by school administrators (Ortiz, 2017; Omay, 2020). This is pinpointed by some previous studies, wherein they concentrate on censorship concerns in college campus papers and examine the factors predicting student journalists' content decisions. One study has found out that censorship administration and students' individual willingness in censoring are not significant predictors of student comfort in publishing controversial materials, but student journalists' roles and perceived content reviewers are significant predictors of student comfort level in producing manipulated information. Consequently, the results recommend helping the student journalists to think at the margin of legal and ethical principles in making content decisions (LoMonte et al., 2013; Cogar, 2021). Despite the retrieved literatures and studies, existing knowledge about the experiences of student journalists

during the COVID-19 pandemic is relatively scarce. Acquiring information in relation to the student journalists' experiences can help people understand their participatory activities and civic engagement, strengthening foundations of developed knowledge and identity (Bobkowski & Miller, 2016; Vogts, 2018).

In this time of crisis, it is important to turn our attention to student journalists and identify the sources of their challenges and ways of survival as they continue their publication roles and responsibilities. Hence, this study seeks to answer the question, what are the experiences of student journalists during the emergence of the global pandemic? The findings of this study demonstrate the environmental, technological, and psychological experiences of student journalists. These will serve as revelation to the students, teachers, school curriculum, information agencies, broadcast centers, future researchers, and other social groups in the community about acquired experiences of student journalists, encompassing challenges to face and opportunities to cherish. The literature reviews and previous studies are key elements for the discussion of the topic, methods, and results. Finally, this study aims to recognize the contributions of student journalists in education, information, and communication.

Methodology

Purpose of the Study and Research Design

This qualitative-phenomenological study described by Sandelowksi (2000) helped to ascertain the experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. It was anchored on a constructivist epistemology, which pursued to examine what is assumed a socially constructed dynamic reality through a precise description of the phenomenon under investigation (Pedroso et al., 2021). The experiences of student journalists were supported by John Dewey's Pragmatic Theory of Experience, in which acquisition of experiences is dependent on (1)

the relationship between the present experience, the past and future ones, (2) the tangible and social context of a person's situation, and (3) an individual's connection to the situation or environment (Stark, 2022).

Respondents

This study was participated by five Editors-in-Chief from different student publication of colleges and universities. The informants were chosen through purposive sampling which also treated as judgmental or selective sampling (Pedroso, 2021). The inclusion criteria of the informants were also employed: a) 18 to 22 years old during the conduct of this study; b) an editor-in-chief in the school publication; c) designated as a student journalist of a Tertiary Higher Education

Institution; and, d) with a minimum of 2 years of service as a student journalist.

Table 1 displays the informants' profiles. The five (5) college student journalists included one (1) male and four (4) female informants. Their age ranged from 18 to 22 years old. The informants had a minimum of two year-service as editors-in-chief. They came from two (2) private and three (3) public higher education institutions. Furthermore, one (1) of them came from the Province of Guimaras; one (1) from Sarangani; one (1) from Antique; and two (2) from Iloilo. The informants were assigned pseudonyms to maintain confidentiality.

Profile of the Informants

College Student Journalist	Age	Sex	Location	Number of Years as a Student Journalist in College/ University Publication	Position	Type of Tertiary Higher Education Institution
Joy	22	Female	Guimaras	3	Editor-in-chief	Private
Ela	21	Female	Antique	3	Editor-in-chief	Private
May	21	Female	Iloilo	5	Editor-in-chief	Public
Lyn	22	Female	Iloilo	4	Editor-in-chief	Public
John	18	Male	Sarangani	2	Editor-in-chief	Public

Instrumentation

The researcher-made written interview form was validated by the panel of experts which was used to gather responses and collect experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. The English language was utilized to organize the semi-structured question and other necessary information to fill out there in. The interview form is created through a Microsoft Word document. The letter for the informant was also attached and followed with the instructions in providing information on the given

template (Kendra, 2020; Pedroso et al., 2021). In addition, critical analysis of literatures, studies, and diagrams were applied to strengthen the foundations of the study's findings (Pedroso, 2021).

Data Gathering Procedure

After a letter of permission to conduct a study was approved by the Dean, data gathering started on January 30, 2022. The researchers were able to find eligible editors-in-chief from college and university publications through Facebook messenger for easy and

convenient communication. The Word document written interview form was sent among the identified informants through email. The informants were given one (1) week to accomplish and submit the written interview form. The researchers are the controllers of information with maintenance of data confidentiality and responsibility.

Data Analysis Procedure

Since the informants submitted their finished written interview forms during the set week of working and submission, the researchers were opted to electronically download and store the gathered documents for direct and fast access. Eventually, the data gathered underwent analysis, comparison, and interpretation using Wolcott's "Transforming Qualitative Data" which organize, categorize, and code the merged data from the informants (Pedroso, 2021). The collected transcripts were systematically organized using the data analysis matrix to identify the environment-related, media technology-related, and psychology-related experiences of the student journalists. The researchers initially concurred that the embedded statements and phrases of the informants would be highlighted and assigned with appropriate codes. Furthermore, the identified codes were classified also into various relevant categories based on the similarities and differences of thought. Meaningful categories were formulated by grouping relevant codes, while different categories were eliminated and grouped based on the different experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. The process of data analysis was finished for two (2) weeks. Lastly, the manuscripts were presented to the informants for data validation (Pedroso et al., 2021).

Reliability

The researchers undertook a thorough data gathering procedures and processes to ensure the reliability of this qualitative-phenomenological study. It also applied pertinent text descriptions, direct quotations

from collected transcripts, and validation of informants' profile (Pedroso et al., 2021). The research making and conducting activities were formally agreed by the researchers, in order to maintain coordination and track study's gradual progress. The results were the accurate interpretation of the participants' responses. Indeed, the integrated review of related literatures and studies to support the findings of the study were carefully included and cited to avoid plagiarism accusations.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers were guided in the ethical conduct of this study by Republic Act 10173, also known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012". It is hereby stated in its Section 8 that publishers, editors, duly accredited reporters of any newspaper, magazine or periodical shall ensure always the value of confidentiality of any personal data that comes to its knowledge and possession. The Section 20 (a) of the said law also emphasized that personal information controller must implement reasonable and proper organizational, physical, and technical measures intended for the protection of personal information against any accidental or unlawful deterioration, modification, and disclosure, as well as against any other unlawful processing. In the succeeding paragraph of the same section, it is further elaborated that the information controller must determine the appropriate level of security by taking into account the nature of the personal information to be protected, the risks represented by the processing, the size of the organization and difficulty of its operations, data privacy practices, and the cost of security imposition (Philippine Government, 2012). The approved letter of information, waivers, and written consent forms were utilized to gather participants' voluntary participation in this study. The researchers maintained utmost anonymity and confidentiality throughout the data gathering process.

Results And Discussion

Results

The student journalists gained the environment-related, media technology-related and psychology-related experiences during the existence of the COVID-19 pandemic. There were six (6) important categories taken from the data transcripts. The student journalists acquired environment-related experiences such as (1) manifest positive outlook in life and (2) render democratic community empowerment services. They also obtained media-technology related experiences such as trying to (3) adjust to unprecedented working transition and (4) encounter misinformation and disinformation issues. Additionally, the global pandemic triggers the student journalists from different universities and colleges to draw psychology-related experiences wherein they (5) confront social communication disparity and (6) endure from self-efficacy enervation.

Environment-related Experiences

The experiences of student journalists were drawn from their ability to respond and deal on prevailing current new normal community situation. There were two (2) examined categories that are relevant to environment-related experiences of the student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic namely (1) manifest positive outlook in life and (2) render democratic community empowerment services.

Manifest Positive Outlook in Life

The emergence of the global pandemic brought destructive impact to the student journalists' adaptation to the new normal community condition, but they remained flexible and resilient to perform and thrive in their duties. This was divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) display situational resilience and (2) exhibit constant decisiveness.

- **Display Situational Resilience**
The COVID-19 pandemic challenged the capacity of student journalists to be flexible

and resilient, in spite of the current unpleasant community situation. They possessed positive abilities to cope and deal from encountered challenges.

Joy: "As resilient student journalists, we're taught to see beauty in everything amidst difficulties."

May: "We experienced a lot of drawbacks but we became stronger in terms of internal and external operations."

- **Exhibit Constant Decisiveness**

Student journalists were dedicated to continue their roles and responsibilities. They were also committed to show to the people that they are strong and capable to rise from various struggles.

May: "With the lack of budget, coverage, travels, and other amenities we have during the face-to-face classes, this pandemic has been a test of passion and commitment to our craft in writing and reportage."

Render Democratic Community Empowerment Services

The student journalists were proactive to extend their efforts and influences both inside the campus and in the community, helping the needy people in the society for social consciousness and development. This was divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) organize educational election campaign and (2) initiate student leadership virtual training.

- **Organize Educational Election Campaign**
The community restrictions and lockdowns were not seen by student journalists as hindrances, rather ways to extend their efforts to the community. They

were goal-driven to implement community activities to promote social awareness.

John: "Meanwhile, as part of the annual Buwan ng Kabataang Sarangan celebration, we launched a month-long young voters' education campaign last August 2021 to assist the youth in our community in making informed choices for the upcoming elections."

- **Initiate Student Leadership Virtual Training**

The work and stay at home scenarios were used by student journalists to propose virtual trainings and seminars. Their willingness to serve and desire to influence the social groups in their community produced beneficial outcomes.

John: "With the rising trend of fake news, we organized a local campaign called Project Verified."

John: "This month-long virtual training aims to equip student-leaders in our community with the mindset, skills, and techniques necessary to improve the information in our environment."

Media Technology-related Experiences

The experiences of student journalists were anchored on the encountered media and technology struggles and challenges in times of the global outbreak. There were two (2) identified categories that are relevant to media technology-related experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic namely (1) adjust to unprecedented working transition and (2) encounter misinformation and disinformation.

Adjust to Unprecedented Working Transition

The big challenge on the part of campus student journalists was the unforeseen transition and migration

of the college or university publication to online community that greatly affected their culture of work. This was divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) embrace online publication modality and (2) react on existing connectivity issues.

- **Embrace Online Publication Modality**

The global pandemic became the primary driver of sudden migration of student publication. The student journalists from different colleges and universities were adjusting from in school to virtual work.

Lyn: "Due to the pandemic, the learning modality has shifted to the online set up which prompted the publication work to also migrate online."

Ela: "Online publication is still a learning curve for me and I hope that the things that I have learned during my time as an EIC will help future writers in our publication."

- **React on Existing Connectivity Issues**

The transition to online modality of publication increased the demand for complete technology devices and internet connection. The lacks and difficulties were inevitable to experience, which student journalists endured while working and meeting online.

Ela: "Connectivity issues have also been brought to my attention many times during meetings and I believe this has hindered some of the participation of our members."

Encounter Misinformation and Disinformation

The world of cyberspace during the COVID-19 was grounded with a lot of misinformation and disinformation that mislead the citizens in the society. This was divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) deliver impartial quality of information and (2) stand with strong personal convictions.

- ***Deliver Impartial Quality of Information***

The online community was dominated with many false information that was intensified during the COVID-19 pandemic. So, the student journalists were doing their utmost to combat the rampant spreading of misinformation and disinformation.

Joy: "Social media is the only option we have and that's one of the biggest challenges, to deliver relevant, factual, and dignified quality student journalism through social media platforms that are dominated by the mainstream and international media where there is rampant use and threats of fake news."

- ***Stand with Strong Personal Convictions***

The salience of truthful and dignified student journalism became important for college student journalists. With this, they ensured objective and factual delivery of news and information for public consciousness.

Joy: "However, we ought to stand still with our convictions without prejudice, bias, and second thoughts."

Psychology-related Experiences

The experiences of student journalists were centered on their social, emotional, and mental conditions during the surge of the COVID-19 pandemic. There were two (2) identified categories that are relevant to psychology-related experiences of the student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic namely (1) confront social communication disparity and (2) endure from self-efficacy enervation.

Confront Social Communication Disparity

The student journalists observed the growing distinction of establishing tactful communication with their family, friends, and fellow staffers. This was

divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) handle challenges on diplomatic relationship and (2) manage prevailing virtual interaction.

- ***Handle Challenges on Diplomatic Relationship***

Physical interaction and social gathering were prohibited in compliance to the implemented health protocols. The student journalists were working a little harder to communicate with their fellow staffers not only for publication matters, but also to establish a good relationship with them.

Ela: "A lot of new members were hired for the new school year and I was really stressing out about how I can establish rapport and a good working relationship with the newbies."

- ***Manage Prevailing Virtual Interaction***

With the imposed community limitations and health advisories, student journalists utilized the online social communication platforms. With the help of these, they maintained their connection, conduct meetings, and discuss important things about the publication.

Lyn: "Furthermore, at the height of the pandemic, morale has also decreased. Zoom or online conferencing fatigue has started to kick in."

Endure from Self-Efficacy Enervation

The drastic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic designed a lot of negative psychological responses for the student journalists that weaken their function and mental health condition. This was divided into two (2) subcategories namely (1) suffer diminishing level of motivation and (2) balance mental health and responsibilities.

- **Suffer Diminishing Level of Motivation**

The absence of social and emotional attachment to other people decreased the motivation of the student journalists. They worked in an isolated and distanced mode, thus affected their interest and energy.

Lyn: “Staffers were losing energy and motivation to work because of isolation.”

- **Balance Mental Health and Responsibilities**

Stress, frustrations, and anxiety were the adverse effects of the global pandemic to the student journalists. They were struggling to balance their mental health and publication responsibilities as they confronted the impacts of the COVID-19.

Lyn: “It took us a year to get the hand of everything and balance our mental health and responsibilities.”

Figure 1. Demonstration of meaningful categories of the study

Discussion

This qualitative-phenomenological study aims to examine the experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. Their experiences were elaborated by three (3) significant themes such as environment-related, media technology-related, and psychology-related. After the deep review of the interview transcripts, six (6) major categories were selected from the informants' responses. The researchers utilized a careful analysis to set the findings of this research in the context of related literatures and the results of previously relevant research studies.

The COVID-19 pandemic has modified the lives of various human races in the world (Wang et al., 2020; Serrano Sarmiento et al., 2021). The health guidelines and protocols in communities have affected the socio-economic, emotional, and educational situation of the entire nations (UNESCO, 2020; Serrano Sarmiento et al., 2021). However, in the research papers of Pavlik (2013) and Perreault (2021), it is noted that the environment with societal norms, protocols, and practices is not a hindrance to cope with the challenges. This perspective is in contrast to Smith et al. (2015) and Tandoc & Takahashi (2018) who have emphasized that journalists are involved in traumatic situations and difficult challenges that weaken their physical immunity. In like manner, it is justified in the study of Buchanan & Keats (2011), Ikizer et al. (2019), and Seely (2020) that they usually display feelings such as guilt, depression, fatigue, pressure, and many others. However, in the study of Moran et al. (2019) and Serrano Sarmiento et al. (2021), it has been mentioned that they have developed coping mechanisms that enable them to display resilience, decisiveness, and adaptability to the present environmental situation of the world. Correspondingly, they have established strategies such as daily exercise, appropriate sleep patterns, balanced diet, and adequate time for relaxation, which are

essential and beneficent to sustain work and individual life (Keats & Buchanan, 2012; Ogunyemi, 2021). These ideas are completely supported by Izquierdo (2021), who emphasized that although the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the roles and functions of student journalists, but they continue to work inside the publication and employ initiatives to participate and provide services to the people in the community. To follow, both the research articles of Brown (2018) and Pedroso et al. (2021) have suggested them to deal on the COVID-19 using their personal dispositions, so that they can definitely continue their work in times of the global pandemic. Their experiences make them competent, determined, and flexible individuals who can rise from difficult situations.

The social media and internet are technology trends, which serve as channels of the student journalists to ameliorate the awareness and engagement of youth in political concerns and issues (Bryant et al., 2020; Lancker & Parolin, 2020; Nicola et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2020; Kwan, 2021). They are similarly willing to influence and promote youth civic and political participation (Landman & Splendore, 2020; Kwan, 2021). In different tone, the study of Beech (2020) and Kwan (2021) confirmed that student journalists are interested to implement community activities but government authorities restrict physical contact. Even so, the research articles of Pollock (2020) and Pedroso et al. (2021) have asserted that they are extraordinary drivers and leaders in this time of crisis. This is agreed by Welton (2020) and Perreault (2021) who stated that student journalists are important to show their accountability as providers of public information. Student journalists are serving the large public with also large number of needs for mass awareness through proper education. They should strike a balance between personal safety and civic responsibility. With this, the study of Beech (2020), Tan (2020), and Kwan (2021) highlighted that they can manifest their community sensitivity by informing the youth of their right and duty as citizens of the nation to exercise their suffrage. On the other hand, Lyons et al. (2020) and

McKillop (2021) responds to their ideas that community actions and services can help student journalists to build closer relationships with their peers and other people in the society. In similar focus, many school publications have implemented virtual trainings and sessions that encouraged the youth involvement. They have learned to use instruments such as reflection and feedback in making experiences and understanding of leadership practices. Participants who have attended in particular leadership trainings conducted by the student journalists, exhibit engagement, and discernment of the leadership learning outcomes (Goucher, 2022). Thus, the student journalists are doing their best to construct links between the youth's efforts and people's situations. With their employed virtual leadership training, the students can increase their contributions for the development of their communities (Kiesh & Peter, 2017; McKillop, 2021).

The transition to online modality has occurred that presented challenges to the teachers, students, and campus journalists of the school publication. The online media and technology platforms required necessary digital literacy skills. Because of this, student journalists face hardship in collaborating with their fellow staffers and submitting finished articles (Burki, 2020; Burns et al., 2020). In agreement with this, there are created pressures to the publications, wherein they modify their work procedures and processes. It is undeniable that it also makes online education and videoconferencing affairs institutionally mandatory (Alfadda and Mahdi, 2021; Pedroso et al., 2021). However, the research papers of Link and Marz (2006) and Burns et al. (2020) have opposed to their conceptions and have affirmed that media, technology, and digital literacies are significant skills and abilities to exhibit by student journalists in order to accomplish their publication duties. To support, student publications reorganization of necessary tasks and responsibilities can strengthen their work system and virtual cooperation (Garcia-Aviles 2021; Quandt & Wahl-Jorgensen, 2021).

Nevertheless, barriers to publication learning and work are inevitable such as undeveloped technical skills, insufficient infrastructure, absence of strategies and support from the people (Last & McGrath, 2018; Ozudogru, 2021). It is also discussed in the research articles of Varma et al. (2021) and Barrero et al. (2021) that some working individuals experience internet access challenges in the midst of the crisis. This is parallel to the study of Balatayo et al. (2021), Baticulon et al. (2021), and Pedroso et al. (2021) who likewise recognize technology-related issues that affect the work of the people. As a result, their participation is impaired that affects the term of work accomplishment (Apriyanti, 2020; Ozudogru, 2021). Despite of these, the study of Mahmud (2010) and Ozudogru (2021) have declared that universities and colleges consider the scarcity of technology resources and internet connection both as challenges to overcome and opportunities to receive. Indeed, it is suggested that government should promote universal access to internet and technology tools, enabling work efficiency and capability (Barrero et al., 2021).

Misinformation and disinformation have been intensified across the different media platforms during the pandemic (Wang et al., 2019; Bastick, 2021; Greene & Murphy, 2021; Massarani et al., 2021). They circulated inside the different platforms of media that call the attention of the democratic citizens (Pickard, 2016; YarivTsfati, 2020). They both invalidate the accuracy and reliability of published or produced information (Madrigal, 2017; Benkler et al., 2018; YarivTsfati, 2020). In the same way, misinformation and disinformation mislead, deceive, and indirect the attention of the large audience that express personal and ideological motives (Jang & Kim, 2018; Cervi & Carrillo-Andrade, 2019; Tejedor et al., 2021). Additionally, they can also destruct and affect the perspectives and behaviors of the public. The absence of gatekeepers online creates a flourishing misinformation (MacDonald & Guirguis, 2015; Shin et al., 2018; Chen & Stoecker, 2020; Vai et al., 2020; Hameleers, 2021). In fact, in the modern era of news

consumption and production, student journalists are considered as frontliners who furnish optimal services to the public (Tandoc, 2017; Balod & Hameleers, 2021). However, the study of Reich & Barnoy (2019) and YarivTsfati (2020) has pinpointed that media and technology challenges become the measurements of student journalists' competence and proficiency to deliver truth in the wake of lies. This is in converse to the ideas of Godler & Reich (2017) who has expressed that journalists in academic and media institutions have obligations to combat such issues through compact verification of information in compliance to journalism principles. To concur, school journalism practices such as fact checking and verification are main strategies to eliminate misinformation and disinformation in the online community (O'Carroll, 2019; YarivTsfati, 2020; Patatt & Rocha, 2020; Brotas et al., 2021; Massarani, et al., 2021). It is further included in the study of Herrero-Diz et al. (2019), Mendiguren et al. (2020), and Tejedor et al. (2021) that journalism students are well-equipped to handle the prevailing media and information issues across the space of social media through definite identification and authentication. They are determined to maintain dignified and worthy journalism in the physical and virtual world. Research article authors Svensson (2017), Balod & Hameleers (2021), Perreault & Perreault (2021), and Massarani et al. (2021) stated that they should strengthen their roles in combating fake news through careful presentation of information. They need also to commit on the formation of democracy through dignified journalism.

Many nations enforce the sanctity of physical distancing which prohibits the world citizens to have minimum and restrictive distance of interaction. This has incremented their engagement and dependence on social media platforms to establish attachment and moment with important people in their life. In the context of the student journalism, it is difficult on the part of journalists to connect and communicate with their fellow staffers. They often use Facebook, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and many other online platforms for

socialization. Although they can see each other on screen, but the emotional connection is not felt entirely (Pliushch, 2018; Vaskovskaya, 2018; Voronova et al., 2020; Olusanya, 2020; Wong, 2021). In like manner, the increasing use of videoconferencing in school and workplaces seems challenging to others who are new in the altered mode of social communication. Many global users complain regarding their experienced frustration from videoconferencing, most of the time is Zoom online platform (Fosslien & Duffy, 2020; Strassman, 2020; Karl et al., 2021). Their ideas are extended in the study of Greenfield (2018) and Greenfield et al. (2021) who have explained that the imposed stay-at-home orders in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic is the main reason of the shift on human values, societal activities, people's relationships, and learning environment. As a result, the student journalists reduced their contact with new and old publication staffers, as well as changes on modes of building relationships. Nevertheless, some journalists in academic learning institution and companies are trying to understand the encountered social dynamics in the present new normal situation. They accept the reality that they have to bridge the social and emotional gaps, in order to continue their work and responsibilities (Kuzminykh & Rintel, 2020; Karl et al., 2021). Additionally, the student journalists are embracing the virtual interaction during meetings, conferences, workshops, and more (Grigoriev et al., 2019; Voronova et al., 2020). Evers et al. (2021) and Greenfield et al. (2021) have mentioned that student journalists respond, in order to survive from the sudden alteration in social interaction. However, they have lost publication cultures that value freedom over constraining rules (Gelfand, 2020; Greenfield et al., 2021). This perspective is different from Aleksieienko-Lemovska (2019) and Voronova et al. (2020) who have compelled that virtual interaction offers advantage of work accomplishment; however, students experience heavy loads in which they became frustrated and pressured while working in the virtual space. So, the distance publication work and processes raise a lot of concerns that require immediate yet

feasible solutions (Tishchenko, 2020; Voronova et al., 2020).

The primary and secondary schools, colleges, and universities are forced to close at the onset of the global pandemic, affecting 98.5% of the world's student population (UNESCO, 2020; Qui et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Salari et al., 2020; Mak, 2021). Consequently, this has reduced the motivation of the ordinary students and student journalists that is evident in developing countries (Parczewska, 2021; Mak, 2021; Zacher & Rudolph, 2021; Rahe & Jansen, 2021). This is coupled with the study of Büssing et al. (2020) and Rahe & Jansen (2021) who stated that the global pandemic has decreased the human satisfaction and physical function, so they are less inclined to work on their tasks and activities. To further support, it is also reported in the United States of America that there is a decline on student journalists' physical activity and work efficiency. The current dilemma can challenge them while balancing their academics, mental health and publication responsibilities (American College Health Association, 2019; Grubic et al., 2020; Mo et al., 2020; Stogner et al., 2020; Vagni et al., 2020; Spoorthy et al., 2020; Maelan et al., 2021; Maher et al., 2021; Rahe & Jansen, 2021). In spite of these, the research papers of Husky et al. (2020), Wang et al. (2020), Grubic et al. (2020), and Bourion-Bedes et al. (2021) have justified that the student journalists overcame severe anxiety and stress, despite home quarantines and community restrictions. On one hand, Wang et al. (2020) and Grubic et al. (2020) have discovered that there are research conducted that assess the mental health impact of the COVID-19, discussing public experiences such as anxiousness and depression. This is the same on the report of the YoungMinds (2020) and research articles of Torales et al. (2020) and Grubic et al. (2020) that many young people have said that the global pandemic worsens the psychological conditions of the people that devitalizes routine, social interaction, and societal activities. This is similarly agreed by the research studies of Osmann et al. (2020) and Osman et al.

(2021) who have revealed that student journalists acquired lack of social and emotional support from colleagues. Moreover, they find difficulties in balancing personal care, mental health condition, and publication responsibilities (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020; Osman et al., 2021). Therefore, the Elevate Education (2020) together with Mak (2021) have advised the schools to implement appropriate measures to address decreasing motivation. Also, the study of Thorell et al. (2021) have expressed that the support of school teachers and parents are crucial on heightening the motivation of student journalists.

As with the related literatures and studies, this current research has many limitations that should be discerned and may be addressed by future studies. First, this study employed a qualitative-phenomenological approach to examine and describe the experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic. Likewise, the findings are only anchored on the experiences of the college student journalists. Second, it is mainly conducted on student journalists from different universities and colleges, which the embedded applications of the findings and implications of the study to student journalism programs may be recognized. Future studies should impart further and extended information of their coping mechanisms and acquired opportunities aside from endured challenges. Finally, the researchers utilized written interview questions, thus there might be a possibility of distortion through self-report bias. Nevertheless, the stated limitations in this study have imparted sufficient data on experiences of student journalists during the COVID-19 pandemic that inform the future researchers about this topic.

The findings of the study have demonstrated the relevant experiences of student journalists in times of the global crisis, which has not been highlighted by the previous researchers. It would have huge contribution and embodiments to all academic fields of research. For other research enthusiasts and aspirants in pressing

issues related to the impacts of the COVID-19 on the lives of various social groups from different institutions, this study can embark significant pieces of understanding and awareness on the various experiences of the college student journalists, promoting resilient and empowered student journalism inside and outside of the school premises. The next challenge that they have to conquer is how to sustain environmental, technological, and psychological adaptations they have manifested to overcome the impacts of the COVID-19 on their roles and responsibilities. In this age of information and communication, student journalists should widen their influence and strengthen their work in covering human stories and news happening in different corners of the global communities. This is a realization for the current and future student journalists that their work as delivery agents of information is uneasy but full of publication's experiences that can amplify their inmost skills and abilities as 21st century citizens.

Conclusion

The experiences of student journalists are reflections of the positive and negative effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. They have practically utilized their encountered hardships as weapons to continue to raise the torch of student journalism. They are committed to serve the academic learning institution and the people in the community, discounting vulnerability of infection. Indeed, student journalists are victims of the global crisis, as well as stewards of civic responsibility and participation. Their job as forefronts of mass information and communication does not end at the tip of a pen and a paper; rather they have extended their efforts to the living social groups in the democratic society. Therefore, the school's curriculum has crucial accountability to uplift the vitality of student journalism and render support and guidance services to maximize their capabilities to rise from any challenging situation.

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